

Influence of Support Services on Inclusive Education of Students with Disabilities in Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria

Jerry, Jummai

Department of Special Education
Faculty of Education
Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria

and

Kanu, Abed

University of Ilorin
Ilorin, Nigeria

Abstract

The study examined the influence of support services on inclusive education of students with disabilities in Nasarawa State University Keffi, survey research design, and descriptive research was adopted to select sample from the population simple random sampling techniques was used to select the respondents which comprises of 40 students with disabilities, 20 lecturers which comprised of 10 special education lecturers and 10 non professional in special education. 3 Research questions and 3 hypotheses were raised to guide the study. Structure questionnaire was adopted to address the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance while simple percentages tables was used to answer research questions, t-test of variance was also used to analysed the hypothesis. The findings revealed that support services encourages wide range of service and enhances learning among students with disabilities, the finding also revealed that students with disabilities in Nasarawa State University are faced with many challenge affecting the effective implementation of enclosure education through support services. Recommendations were made to profer solution to students with disabilities in Nasarawa State University.

Keywords: Inclusive Education; Supportive Services; Students with Disabilities

Introduction

Every student with disabilities has equal right to learn alongside their non disabled counterparts in an inclusive environment, students with disabilities need special services to cope with their academic endeavors and livelihood. The United Nations (2015) approximated that around 1 billion people globally experience one or more sensory, physical intellectual or mental health disabilities. Disabled students experience unique challenges based on the area of disabilities, however, there are different kind of services available that can address their learning needs. Morina (2017) emphasized that, more tertiary institutions

focus on mainstreaming of disabled students, rather than inclusion of this students in tertiary institutions, because inclusive education provides reasonable accommodation and support service for disabled students so as to provide absolute participation and equal opportunities in teaching and learning. Hence, the university system must be designed to address the diverse characteristics and specific needs of students with disabilities within the standard university framework.

According to the United Nations' Article 24 of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (2006), equal opportunities in education for individuals with disabilities must be prioritized. The framework requires states to guarantee reasonable accommodations for individual needs and implement specialized support services within inclusive educational environments. Following the United Nation Declaration, Nigeria government ensures that structural barriers are removed and all learners receive learning in the same environment regardless of any difficulties or degree of severity. Inclusive education is a system whereby students with disabilities receives quality teaching and learning alongside their non-disabled peers in the same classroom settings, according to Mitchell D. (2005), inclusive education is an educational approach that embraces all types of student diversity within schools. It requires significant modifications to content, methods, structure, and strategies, all aimed at ensuring that all categories of students in the university are supported. Inclusive education cannot be over emphasized due to its importance in the educational system. It promotes opportunities for learners' equalities regardless of their disabilities and enable students to foster a culture of inclusivity, promoting social and academic growth, preparing them for different endeavors globally.

Inclusive education is very difficult to implement due to its complexity in meeting all the needs of individuals, or students in various schools or institutions of learning (Mitche D. 2005). The author further stated that major reasons for these challenges include high cost of special equipment that are used in supporting Students with impairments in schools especially in the higher institutions. There are inadequate professionals which affect the smooth running of inclusive education practices in Nigeria. In view of the above, the study reviewed the influence of supportive services on inclusive education of students with disabilities in Nasarawa State University. Students with impairments cannot be successfully achieved their educational career without receiving support services during teaching and learning in a regular classroom settings.

Support services include a range of assistive technologies utilized in education to assist students with disabilities, including devices like Braille embossers, which is use for transforming ordinary printed materials to braille prints for the blinds. Another assistive technologies is called audiometer, which is used for testing hearing level for the deaf. Talking kits for the learning disabled. Similarly, Habor (2009) viewed

that, educational institute at all level need to develop programmes that accommodate inclusive education policies towards supporting students with disability in attaining their right to accessibility in achieving appropriate educational goals. Center for disabilities studies and support services is a facility where specialize equipments are kept and arrange with different professionals that are stationed to offer support and special services for students with impairments in an inclusive class.

However, Habor (2009) Explained that support services is a type of services offered to students with impairments which includes assistive technology, for example, transcription and production of special materials considering all the learning needs of students with impairments are met during teaching, learning and examination. Support services also include creation of awareness and sensitization of students and community at large on disability issues. The University of Dar es Salaam (UDSM), a public institution established in 1961 and located in the Ubungo District of Tanzania, provides technical assistance to non-disabled lecturers to enhance their capacity for teaching students with disabilities within inclusive educational settings. Additionally, the university offers counseling services to students with disabilities and ensures the provision of both social and physical accommodations to support their participation in teaching and learning processes. As stated by UDSM (2022), the institution has formulated a policy on disability rights and special needs education aimed at safeguarding non-discriminatory practices and promoting inclusive access to university facilities and services for both students and staff with disabilities. There are concrete adjustments put in place for staff and students with disabilities, to enhance their productivity and equal opportunity in the aspect of recruitment, retention, progression, positive network and creating better learning and conducive environment that promote University System.

Similarly, studies have shown that in supporting students with disabilities in an inclusive settings, centers for disabilities and support services are faced with numerous challenges, this statement was supported by Sun & Xin (2020) that in supporting students with impairments the coordinating unit are challenged with many constraints which include administrative bottle neck, resistance and un-cooperation from the faculty and the departmental staff, unavailability of disability policies, inadequate assistive technology, and ignorance on the side of staff, in accessible infrastructures, lack of transportation system for students with disabilities, communication barrier, unfriendly learning and working environment, health problems, lack of knowledge on application of assistive technology, poor networking among students and staff of the institution and management leadership, based on the above mention challenges can affect the provision of support services to students with impairments. Who are students with impairments in an inclusive university environment?

Students with impairments are seen as those persons with various types of impairment who deviate significantly either physical, mental or sensory as a result of impairment, and are deprived from performing certain task, for example, a person who have visual impairment cannot perform task that involve sight for example, driving, carpentry and others. A hearing-impaired person cannot speak orally due to dysfunction of the ear and vocal cavity. Students with disabilities cannot effectively achieve academic task without technical support services. According to United Nation (2006) conformed that disabilities is refer to a complex and multifaceted word that comprises of different aspect of human functioning, World health Organization (2001) supported that disability is a generic term that described impairment as an activity limitation and participation restrictions in the body structures or functions, difficulty in performing tax and problem in life situation of individuals with disability.

Students with disabilities require specialized support services to facilitate their academic adjustment and help them achieve their educational objectives. Van (2020) discovered that many assistive technologies and other perspective are offered to support students with disabilities for educational development. The author further noted that inadequate funding and the lack of assistive technology within the Centre for Disabilities and Support Services have hindered the effective implementation of support services for students with disabilities. In light of this, the present study examines the influence of support services on the promotion of inclusive education for students with disabilities at Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nasarawa.

Statement of the Problem

Students with impairment attends university education but are faced with familiar problem of exclusion, stigmatization and discrimination, inappropriate curricular, insufficient professional staff, inadequate assistive technology, lack of trained staff and general poor attitudes of non-disabled student towards students with impairments in an inclusive classroom. Inclusive education allows integration among students with disabilities in the institution for better equality and socialization, yet, inclusivity is not yet fully practice in various institution of learning. Consequently, this research explores the role of support services provided by the Special Education Department, in collaboration with the Centre for Disability Studies and Support Services, in enhancing the educational experience of students with disabilities at Nasarawa State University. Addressing this identified gap, the researcher conducted a study to assess the impact of these support services on inclusive education for students with disabilities at Nasarawa State University, Keffi.

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate the influence of support services on inclusive education of students with disabilities in Nasarawa State University Keffi, specific objectives were to:

1. identify the influence of support services to students with impairments in Nasarawa State University Keffi
2. identify the impact of inclusive education for students with impairments in Nasarawa State University Keffi
3. To identify challenges hindering the provision of support services for students with impairments in higher institutions
4. To make possible recommendation to the challenges faced by students with impairments in Nasarawa State University.

Research Questions

These following questions were stated below:

1. To what extend does support services influence students with impairments in Nasarawa State University Keffi?
2. To what extend does inclusive education influence students with impairments in Nasarawa State University Keffi?
3. What challenges hinder the effective provision of support services for students with disabilities in higher education institutions?

Statement of Hypotheses

To guide the study, the following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at the 0.05 level of significance.

1. Support services have no significant influence on students with disabilities at Nasarawa State University, Keffi.
2. Inclusive education has no significant influence on students with impairments in Nasarawa State University Keffi.
3. There are no challenges encountered by students with hearing impairment in Nasarawa State University Keffi.

Scope/ Delimitation of the Study

The study is limited to students with impairments at Nasarawa State University, Keffi Local Government Area (LGA) of Nasarawa State. Only one tertiary institution was selected from the listed tertiary institutions of learning by the Ministry of Education. Given the limitations of time and resources, this study could not encompass all tertiary institutions within Keffi Local Government Area. Consequently, data collection was restricted to a selected sample, which may not fully represent the entire population within the LGA during the research process. The study was limited to lecturers in the department of Special Education as well as students with impairments. Major variable for this study includes: Inclusion, support services, students with disabilities, Nasarawa State University Keffi.

Methodology

This study employed a survey research design to gather relevant data from respondents regarding the influence of support services on inclusive education for students with disabilities at Nasarawa State University, Keffi. The design was considered appropriate because it gave the researcher the opportunity to meet the respondents one on one (close contact) to collect data from a sample population and none of the variables was manipulated. It also enabled the researcher to use larger population sample. The Study was carried out by Special Education Department, Nasarawa State University, Keffi LGA of Nasarawa State. The study used simple random sampling techniques to select total population which comprises of forty (40) respondents with disabilities, 20 lecturers, which 10 were professionals while 10 are non-professionals' lecturers to participate in the study. The study utilized a researcher-designed questionnaire as the main tool for data collection. To verify its validity, professionals in the fields of educational research, measurement, and evaluation thoroughly assessed the instrument for both face and content validity. Data analysis involved the use of simple percentage tables to respond to the research questions, while the null hypotheses were examined using t-test analysis at a 0.05 level of significance.

Findings and Discussion

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1

Support services have no significant influence on students with disabilities in Nasarawa State University Keffi

Table 1 Showing t-test statistics on influence of Support services on students with disabilities in Nasarawa State University Keffi

Variable	N	Mean	Std	t. Cal.	P-Value	Sig
Supportive services	60	30	2.72	8.14	0.000	0.05
students with disabilities	60	30	2.74			

From Table 1, the findings revealed that the sample size of 60 respondents mean score of supportive services and students with disabilities recorded 30 each respectively, standard deviation recorded 2.72 and 2.74, the calculated t-value was given as 8.14, P-value is 0.000 which is less than 0.05 level of significant, therefore, hypothesis one tested is rejected, this implies that supportive services has significant influence on students with disabilities in Nasarawa State University Keffi.

Hypothesis 2

Inclusive education has no significant influence on students with impairments at Nasarawa State University, Keffi

Table 2 Shows t-test statistics on Influence of Inclusive Education on Students with impairments in Nasarawa State University Keffi

Variable	N	Mean	Std	t. Cal.	P-Value	Sig	Decision
Inclusive education	60	301.8	4	6.15	0.000	0.05	Rejected
Students with Disabilities	60	30	1.86				

From table 2, the sample size of 60 respondents, the mean score of inclusive education and students with disabilities recorded 30 and 30 respectively, standard deviation is 1.84 and 1.86, the calculated t-value was given as 6.15, P-value is 0.000 which is less than 0.05 level of significant, therefore, hypothesis 1 tested is rejected, this implies that inclusive education has significant influence on students with disabilities in Nasarawa State University Keffi.

Hypothesis 3

The provision of support services for students with disabilities in higher education institutions is not significantly affected by any challenges.

Table 3: T-test Analysis of the Challenges Affecting the Provision of Support Services for Students with Impairments in Higher Education Institutions

Variable	N	Mean	Std	t. Cal.	P-Value	Sig	Decision
Challenges to Support services	60	30	1.15	3.42	0.000	0.05	Rejected
Students with disabilities	60	30	1.17				

From table 3, the sample size of 60 respondents, the mean score of Challenges to Support services and students with disabilities recorded 30 and 30 respectively, the standard deviation recorded 1.15 and 1.17, calculated t-value was given as 3.42, P-value is 0.000 which is less than 0.05 level of significant, therefore, hypothesis 3 tested is rejected, this implies that there are challenges hindering the provision of support services for students with disabilities in higher education institutions.

Discussion of Findings

Based on the analysis carried out, the findings of hypothesis one was tested and confirmed that supportive services have significant influence on students with disabilities in Nasarawa State University Keffi. This result aligns with Cohen (2018), who emphasized that support services are vital resources designed to assist individuals with disabilities in overcoming challenges, enhancing their well-being, and fostering greater inclusion within society. These services span a range of areas, including healthcare, financial assistance, housing, and access to relevant information, all tailored to meet the diverse needs of persons with disabilities while encouraging independence and self-determination. Such services may be provided by government bodies or other institutions and are intended to ensure active participation of individuals with disabilities in community and societal life. Some of these supports are legally mandated, others involve the use of assistive technologies that have simplified service delivery, and many are commercially available to both individuals with disabilities and the general public.

Assistive technology plays a crucial role in enabling individuals with disabilities to engage fully in all aspects of society, including education, employment, and recreational activities. A variety of disability-related services exist to empower people with disabilities by fostering a sense of optimism, capability, and

direction. These technologies—whether devices, software, or specialized equipment—are designed to help individuals carry out tasks that might otherwise be difficult or impossible without assistance. Supporting people with disabilities can take many forms, such as creating inclusive job opportunities, improving infrastructure accessibility, offering adaptive tools, ensuring access to quality education, and providing both financial and medical support. Such efforts contribute to building a more inclusive and equitable society, one that upholds the principles of diversity and human rights. Assistive technologies range from basic household tools to more advanced equipment, including pressure-relief mattresses, powered wheelchairs, hearing aids, artificial limbs, and voice-controlled software. The result of hypothesis two was tested and confirmed that Inclusive education has significant influence on students with disabilities in Nasarawa State University Keffi, this finding is in agreement with Alberta Education (2016) which state that inclusive education is an important practice that help in strengthening the capacity of education system to reach out to all learners. Inclusion is regarded as an ongoing process aimed at recognizing and meeting the varied needs of all learners including children, adolescents, and adults by fostering greater involvement in education, culture, and community life, while actively working to minimize or eliminate forms of exclusion. This approach calls for adjustments in curriculum content, teaching methods, institutional structures, and educational strategies, all guided by a unified vision that embraces every child within the relevant age group. At its core, inclusion reflects a belief that mainstream education systems bear the responsibility of ensuring learning opportunities for all students, regardless of their individual differences.

The analysis of the third hypothesis confirmed that several challenges impede the effective delivery of support services to students with disabilities in higher education institutions. This outcome is consistent with the observations of English K.M. (1993), who identified significant barriers to providing such services. Among these are insufficient funding to implement programs specifically designed for students with disabilities. These students are often perceived as presenting complex needs that make service provision more demanding and costly. Acquiring essential educational materials, adaptive technologies, specialized sanitary facilities, and trained personnel requires substantial financial resources—resources that many institutions struggle to secure. Consequently, universities are frequently unable to provide the necessary infrastructure and professional support. Additionally, the lack of administrative commitment at various institutional levels contributes to the problem. University administrators and faculty members often overlook the specific needs of students with disabilities, which further limits the availability of tailored support services. Moreover, because the population of students with severe disabilities tends to be relatively small, institutional priorities often favour the majority. As a result, the concerns and voices of students with disabilities are marginalized. Supporting this view, Van (2020) also emphasized that the lack

of assistive technology continues to be a critical factor limiting the effectiveness of support services for students with disabilities in higher education.

Conclusion

The study highlighted several challenges in implementing practical inclusive education. Notably, there appears to be a significant gap between the ideals of inclusion and their actual application, reflecting a lack of genuine political commitment. Difficulties in implementation are also linked to ongoing debates about how inclusive education should be defined and operationalized, including disagreements on which student groups should be prioritized, issues of access, and a general lack of policy coherence. Furthermore, many educators demonstrate limited competency in inclusive teaching practices, which further impedes progress.

The study concluded that support services have a meaningful impact on promoting inclusive education for students with disabilities at Nasarawa State University, Keffi. It was found that such services are generally perceived to enhance students' academic engagement, increase retention rates, and support the successful completion of their studies. However, there remains limited evidence on the actual outcomes of reasonable adjustments or the effectiveness of institution-wide learning supports for students with disabilities. According to the findings, while some students reported that certain forms of support were beneficial, others found them less effective, with opinions varying on what constituted valuable assistance. The study suggests that future research should explore the effectiveness of different types of support in terms of student experience, course success, and cost-efficiency.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. The universities should organize training programs on disability education to enhance lecturers' ability to deliver flexible and inclusive instruction that meets the diverse needs of students with disabilities.
2. Institutions should hire qualified special education professionals to assess students' needs and coordinate appropriate categories of support and services.
3. University management should ensure the availability of specialized equipment, professional support staff, and accessible infrastructure to facilitate effective teaching and learning for students with disabilities.
4. The Ministry of Education should assume a stronger supervisory role and promote increased accessibility and institutional support for students with disabilities in higher education.

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